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MUHAMMAD WASEEM ASLAM

*KM Animal Clinic & Surgery, Sdn. Bhd., 68100, Batu Caves, Selangor, Malaysia.***GASTRIC DILATATION VOLVULUS IN A CAT**

A 7-year old, castrated male Domestic short hair cat was presented with a primary complaint of abdominal distension, and frothy salivation (over 24 hours). Physical examination findings include serous ocular discharge and unresolved mucoïd nasal discharge (treated for the past 4 days) with mild respiratory distress and asymmetrical abdominal distension, predominantly on the left side. Furthermore, the abdomen was tympanic at percussion. The mucous membrane was congested with mild bradycardia and poor pulsation were noted; that led to the hypothesis that the cat was undergoing distributive shock (although 39°C, normal temperature) based on the clinical presentation of this cat. Minimum database for this particular patient showed left shift with bands, lymphocytosis and monocytosis as conspicuous findings with mild increase in blood urea nitrogen and creatinine levels. Serology testing was positive for *Chlamydomphila felis*. Mild elevation of lactate was a salient marker for shock indication. The cat was initially managed with oxygen-therapy and intravenous fluid therapy with Hartmann's solution (HM) and antibiotics. Lateral abdominal radiography revealed presence of intra-abdominal dilated stomach displacing the pylorus dorsally, dilated esophagus with gas filled intestinal loops. A diagnosis of gastric dilatation volvulus (GDV) was highly suspected based on the abdominal radiographic findings. Decompression of the stomach was performed using a nasogastric tube of 1.2 mm diameter. Approximately 6 hours after presentation, exploratory surgery was done. The stomach was found approximately 180° rotated. Mild haemorrhagic changes without any obvious necrotic properties were seen on the fundus of the stomach. Incisional gastropexy was performed to fix the stomach with right side abdominal wall to restore its normal position. Nasogastric tube feeding was started 6 hours post-surgery with prescription diet a/d. The cat began to consume food orally 12 hours postoperatively and was discharged 48 hours later. GDV did not recur with close monitoring up to 1.5 years after surgery. Prognosis in this case was good mainly because the cat was managed intensively during the initial shock stages with the assistance of diagnostic imaging.